

THERMO-SENSITIVE HYDROGEL COMPOSITE FOR CONTROLLED DELIVERY OF DRUGS WITH FUNCTIONALIZED CARBON NANOTUBES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have potential applications in biomedicine as pharmaceutical excipients for creating drug delivery systems attributed to their intrinsic physicochemical features. Surface functionalized carbon nanotubes (f-CNTs) exhibit biocompatibility, and low cytotoxicity. In this work, CNTs were modified by covalent and non-covalent methods. The f-CNTs were ulteriorly entrapped within a thermo-sensitive hydrogel based on poly (N-isopropylacrylamide-co-N-vinylpyrrolidone) copolymer. The morphology of the CNTs, f-CNTs, f-CNTs/hydrogel composites were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The temperature sensitivity, and capacity of loading and release of a small molecule drug of this drug delivery system were investigated. Through the above test, the availability of the smart composite for controlled delivery of drugs was explored.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been touted as meritorious materials in different applications, due to its unsurpassed properties consisting of their high mechanical strength, large specific surface area, and lightweight[1, 2]. These nanostructured materials have the versatility to act as biomaterials attributed to the foregoing virtues, such as they have been used as drug delivery systems for attaching drugs to the surface or loading into the CNTs[3-6].

The dispersion of CNTs in solvents affects their applications. The study from Al-Jamal et al. [7] has shown that good dispersibility of CNTs in aqueous solutions can substantially reduce cytotoxicity of CNTs. Many methods have been proposed for improving the dispersion of CNTs in different solvents, of which the functionalization of carbon nanotubes is a commonly availability and effective method[8, 9]. And the functionalization can be divided into covalent functionalizations and noncovalent ones[10-12]. For instance, carboxyl (COOH-) and amino (NH₂-) that has been widely used to functionalize the CNTs, that kind of method is regarded as the covalent modifications. In addition, the functionalization by surfactants or polymers is usually non covalent. The surfactants are connected with CNTs by intermolecular forces such as hydrogen bonding and Van der Waals forces or π - π interaction, thus help improving the dispersion of CNTs in different solvents in varying degrees.

TritonX-100 as a nonionic surfactant has been applied to modify the CNTs, and the results showed that carbon nanotubes can be well dispersed in aqueous solution after the functionalization[13].

In recent years, hydrogels have been widely used in many fields, especially in biomedicine as drug delivery system and tissue engineering scaffold[14-16]. Hydrogel is a macromolecule polymer with three-dimensional network structure and it's cross-linked by multiple forces such as covalent bonds, hydrogen bonding, Van der Waals interactions and even physical entanglements. A great number of hydrophilic groups and hydrophobic groups exist in the hydrogel. When the hydrogel is immersed in an aqueous solution, the hydrophilic group combines with water, trapping the water molecule in the network, while the hydrophobic group expands in water simultaneously. In this way, drugs can be encapsulated in the network structure of hydrogels in order to avoid the effect of external hostile environment and slowly release drugs at sick places.

Environmentally sensitive hydrogels can be affected by the external stimuli (such as temperature, pH, light, electricity, and pressure) and give respond with physicochemical changes[17-19]. Lower critical solution temperature (LCST) is an important indicator for temperature sensitive hydrogels. Around the LCST, the swelling-deswelling behavior of hydrogels will have a significant change with the alteration of temperature. These temperature sensitive hydrogels, which is called smart hydrogels, have turned out to be one of the most interesting topics [20-23]. The study has pointed out that poly (N-isopropylacrylamide-co- N-vinylpyrrolidone) copolymer has the LCST near 37 °C (close to the human body temperature), which makes it possible for the application as a drug delivery system[24].

In recent years, f-CNTs and hydrogels have been used to prepare composite materials for drug delivery system[25]. Liu et al.[26] have developed a novel carboxyl functionalized CNTs/poly(acrylamide-co-sodium methacrylate) nanocomposite hydrogel for drug controlled release and tissue engineering, which exhibits better swelling capability, higher pH sensitivity and good repeatability. Covalent modified CNTs have been applied in most studies and non-covalent CNTs are rarely mentioned. By the covalent methods, interfacial adhesion between the CNTs and the functionalized groups is much stronger, but the structure of CNTs will be destroyed. While by the non-covalent methods, the functionalized CNTs will maintain the relatively complete structure, with weaker interfacial adhesion between CNTs and the modifiers. In addition, the introduction of macromolecules may bring new performance to the f-CNTs/hydrogel composite. The effect of the two kinds of functionalized CNTs on the composite is hard to predicted.

In this work, as received purified CNTs, COOH-CNTs and TritonX-100-CNTs have been chosen and ulterior entrapped within a thermo-sensitive hydrogel based on poly (N-isopropylacrylamide-co-N-vinylpyrrolidone) copolymer to prepare the thermo-sensitive hydrogel composite. The morphology of the CNTs, f-CNTs, f-CNTs/hydrogel composites were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The equilibrium swelling ratio, deswelling kinetics, and capacity of loading and release of salicylic acid (as the model drug) were investigated. The effect of the covalent and the non-covalent modified CNTs on the properties of hydrogel composites have been discussed.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

The pristine MWCNTs and the plasma-COOH functionalized MWCNTs used in this work were purchased from XFNANO Company (Nanjing, China). They were both with diameter of 10-20 nm

and length of 10-30 μm , and used as supplied. Polyethylene glycol octylphenol ether (TritonX-100, Deng Feng, Tianjin) were used to non-covalent functionalize MWCNTs.

N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAAm) and N-vinylpyrrolidone (NVP) supplied from Aladdin and Adamas Reagent Co.,Ltd, respectively, were used as monomers to fabricate the hydrogel. N,N'-methylenebisacrylamide (BisAAM) employed as crosslinking agent was purchased from Adamas Reagent Co.,Ltd. Potassium persulfate and sodium hydrogen sulfite used as the redox system were purchased from Aladdin and Kemiou Chemical Reagent Co (Tianjin, China), respectively. And they were all used as received.

2.2 Preparation of the f-CNTs

The TritonX-100 functionalized CNTs were prepared by the following steps: 400 mg of a mixture of CNTs and TritonX-100 (1:1 weight ratio) were dispersed in 10 mL distilled water by the SONICS VCX800 sonicator for 30 min (at 160W). Then they were kept in ultrasonic bath for 1 h. TritonX-100 functionalized CNTs was obtained after drying at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 48 h.

2.3 Preparation of the f-CNTs/hydrogel composites

7.0 mmol of NIPAAm and 1.5 mmol of NVP were dissolved in 10mL distilled water. The CNTs or the f-CNTs (1 mg, i.e., 0.1%,w/w, relative to the monomers) were dispersed in the solution by the SONICS VCX800 sonicator for 15 min (at 160W). BisAAM (as cross-linking agent at 2.0 mol% based on the monomers) was added to form a monomer solution. Then dried nitrogen was bubbled through the monomer solution for 50 min. After that, the free radical polymerization of the Poly (NIPAAm-co-NVP) hydrogel was carried out and the f-CNTs/hydrogel composites were obtained in a glass vessel at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 48h. Potassium persulfate and sodium hydrogen sulfite were used as the redox system. After the reaction, the synthesized composites were immersed into the distilled water at room temperature for at least 4 days, and refresh the water every several hours to leach the unreacted monomers and impurities out as far as possible. All the samples were cut into cylinder pieces approximately 8 mm in diameter and 5mm in thickness for the following studies.

Similar preparation conditions were applied for the pure hydrogel without the f-CNTs as the control group.

2.4 Morphological analysis

The hydrogel and composites samples were equilibrated in distilled water at room temperature (about 22 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) before drying treatment. And they were freeze-dried at - 42 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 days until all the solvent was sublimed. Then the obtained productions were fractured carefully. The interior morphology of the samples was studied by a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, MIRA3LMH, TESCAN, a.s.). Before the observation, the specimens were coated with gold for 50 s. The morphology of the CNTs and f-CNTs were also observed by SEM.

2.5 Temperature responsive properties

2.5.1 Measurement of equilibrium swelling ratio of the composites

The samples were swollen in distilled water over a temperature range from 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 46 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (that covers the expected range of LCST of the hydrogels) for the study of equilibrium swelling ratio (ESR).

To study the swelling ratio, the gravimetric method was used[27, 28]. Pre-weighed samples were swollen in distilled water until the equilibrium at each predetermined temperature for at least 24 h, then the samples were removed and blotted with moistened filter paper in order to remove excess water on the surface and weighed. And the equilibrium swelling ratio was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Swelling ratio} = W_s / W_d \quad (1)$$

where W_s is the weigh of water in the swollen gel at a particular temperature and W_d is the weight of dry sample.

2.5.2 Measurement of deswelling kinetics of the composites

The deswelling kinetics were measured gravimetrically at 48 °C after wiping off the water on the surface with moistened filter paper[28]. The samples were equilibrated in distilled water at room temperature for 48 h. The changes of the weight were recorded with regular time intervals during the de-swelling. And water retention is defined as follows:

$$\text{water retention} = [(W_t - W_d)/W_s] \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where W_t is the weight of the water in the gel at regular time intervals and other symbols are the same as defined above. The volume phase transition temperature (VPTT) of the samples was determined as the inflexion point of the curves of swelling ratio versus temperature.

2.6 Drug loading and release experiments

In this study, salicylic acid (SA) was taken as the model drug to perform the Drug loading and release experiments. Each sample was immersed in 10 ml aqueous solution with SA (1.5mg/ml), and kept soaked for seven days at 37 °C[29]. Then the SA-loaded composite was removed, and washed with distilled water. The amount of SA remained in the solutions was measured by the UV-Vis spectrophotometry (UV-1800PC, Meipuda, Shanghai) (at $\lambda=295\text{nm}$) with a calibration curve that was made previously. And the concentration of SA in each sample was calculated according to the Eq (3):

$$SA_{\text{Loaded}} = [SA]_a - [SA]_b \quad (3)$$

where $[SA]_b$ and $[SA]_a$ and the concentration of SA in the solution before and after the loading.

The drug release experiments were performed by soaking SA loaded simples in distilled water at 37 °C, 3.0 ml of the release solution was moved out at predetermined time intervals. And the concentration of SA solution was measured spectrophotometrically (at $\lambda=295\text{nm}$).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology of the CNTs and the f-CNTs

Figure 1: Scanning electron micrographs of the CNTs with different magnifications: the pure CNTs (panel A and D), the COOH-CNTs (panel B and E), the TritonX-100-CNTs (panel C and F).

The morphology of pristine and functionalized CNTs observed by SEM was shown in Figure 1(A, B, C). The carboxyl functionalized CNTs was modified by covalent way. And the CNTs on panel C were functionalized by TritonX-100 noncovalently. Specifically, the hydrophobic carbon chains of TritonX-100 were connected with CNTs by Van der Waals forces or π - π interaction. And the free hydrophilic groups of TritonX-100 supplied the water solubility, which provided the CNTs with better dispersibility in aqueous solution. As we see from the SEM images, the COOH-CNTs (panel B) were almost identical to the pristine CNTs in morphology. The TritonX-100 functionalized CNTs enlarged the diameter and prevented shortening the length of CNTs. Meanwhile, as the observation showed at contractible magnification (D, E, F), the COOH-CNTs and the pristine one looks more compact than the surfactant functionalized CNTs which is expanding and loose. In other words, the CNTs were better unfolded by the functionalization of TritonX-100.

3.2 Morphology of the pure hydrogel and f-CNTs/hydrogel composites

In Figure 2, the panel A, B and C display the SEM micrographs taken from the fractured cross-sections of the pure hydrogel and the composites with the COOH-CNTs and the TritonX-100-CNTs. The pure CNTs/hydrogel was not observed because the pristine CNTs were agglomerated at the bottom of the hydrogel. It is obvious that these samples possess relatively large specific areas and micro pore sizes. By compared with the pure hydrogel, the composites (panel B and

C) also exhibit a large number of mesh walls. But the mesh walls in the case of the functionalized CNTs/hydrogel composites become thinner than the pure hydrogel, which could be attributed to the addition of the f-CNTs. The formation of the cross-linking among the polymer may be blocked due to the filling of the f-CNTs, which results in the decrease of the cross-linking density and the porous density, and the enhance of the porous size[26]. The addition of the f-CNTs makes the micro pores become larger slightly than the pure hydrogel, which provides greater space for the storage of water during the swelling. And we can also see that the characteristic patterns of the f-CNTs couldn't be discerned clearly not only in empty spaces, but also in mesh walls, even magnifying the images.

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrographs of the synthetic hydrogels: the control hydrogel (panel A), the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite (panel B), the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite (panel C).

It implies that the CNTs are well dispersed in the hydrogels and the thick mesh walls are encapsulated or wrapped on the surface of the CNTs. In combination with the tests of the temperature sensitive properties and the drug release in this paper, the interpenetrating of the f-CNTs plays an important role in the changing of the properties of hydrogel although the composites are with low content of f-CNTs.

3.3 Temperature responsive properties

3.3.1 Equilibrium swelling ratio of the composites

All the composites samples can be swollen in water without being dissolved by water. As we saw in the temperature sensitive properties testing, the samples kept transparent and homogeneous below the temperature of about 30 °C. When it was raised to a higher temperature (e.g., >40 °C), the sample began to shrink and the hydrogels changed to be cloudy with white fog on the surfaces, which indicated that the volume transition occurred in this temperature range. When cooled, the sample reswelled and became clear again. This swelling-reswelling behavior that is reversible with the change of temperature is characteristic of the thermo-sensitive hydrogels.

Figure 3: Equilibrium swelling ratio of the hydrogel and the composites in the temperature range from 22 °C to 52 °C

Figure 3 shows the temperature-dependent equilibrium swelling ratio of the samples with the temperature range from 22 °C to 52 °C. As we can see, all the samples had the similar sigmoid curves of swelling ratio versus temperature, i.e., there was a quick decrease of swelling ratio as the temperature increased, and which is the unique characteristic of volume phase transition of the smart hydrogels these are thermo-sensitive. The volume phase transition temperature (VPTT) of the samples was determined as the inflexion point of the sigmoid curves of swelling ratio versus temperature, and the sigmoid curves were fitted by the plot fits of 3th degree polynomial, in the basic fitting tools of the Matlab R2016b. And the VPTT were 35.4 °C, 35.1 °C, 34.2 °C, for the control hydrogel, COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite, and TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite, respectively. All the VPTT are at about 35 °C, which is quite close to human body temperature.

At 22 °C (below the VPTT), the swelling ratio of the control hydrogel is 15.18. It's exhibited that the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite displayed higher swelling ratio (17.75) and the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite displayed lower swelling ratio (11.34) than the plain hydrogel. The enhanced swelling ratio of the composite is attributed to the presence of TritonX-100 (the non-ionic surfactant), which includes generous ether bonds that are consisted of oxygen-containing groups and the ether bonds are hydrophilic. When the temperature is below the VPTT, more water has been imbibed by the hydrophilic groups as the hydrogel absorbs water. On the other hand, TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite has a larger pore size as we see from the SEM, which provides greater space for water storage. As a result, introduction of large pores and the hydrophilic groups offer high swelling capability to the hydrogel composite by the TritonX-100-CNTs, which is good to the use of hydrogel as drug delivery. Although the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite has a

larger pore size than the control group, the hydrophilic group is not strong enough to accommodate more water.

For the control hydrogel, when the temperature ranged from 22 °C to 52 °C, the swelling ratio was reduced from 15.18 to 0.38, i.e., 97.5 wt% absorbed water was released when the volume phase transition occurred. Meanwhile, 97.2 wt% and 96.4 wt% of water absorbed in the composites was released for the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite and the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite when the temperature was raised from 22 °C to 52 °C. These materials were all sensitive to the change of temperature. In other words, the introduction of the COOH-CNTs and the TritonX-100-CNTs did not destroy the temperature sensitivity of the materials.

3.3.2 Deswelling kinetics of the composites

Figure 4: Deswelling kinetics of the hydrogel and composites at 48 °C

Deswelling kinetics is one of the temperature responsive properties of hydrogel. In order to evaluate the deswelling behavior of the materials, all the samples were soaked in water at 48 °C and measured gravimetrically at variable times since the smart hydrogels can shrink and release the water absorbed when heating up to the temperature above the VPTT. Figure 4 illustrates the deswelling curves of the hydrogels. At the beginning of the deswelling, the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite had the fastest rate of water loss and the control hydrogel had the slowest, which is attributed to the bigger micro pore sizes of the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel and the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel. Then as time went on (about 1h later), it is interesting to note that the deswelling curve of the control hydrogel became beneath that of the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite,

may because that the collapse degree of the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite is higher than that of the pure hydrogel and the collapse arrests the release of the water from the hydrogel composite. The observation indicates that the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite displayed much lower stable water retention than the control one and the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite had higher water retention under the identical condition. That is to say, the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite were capable of releasing much more absorbed water than the plain hydrogel and the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite.

3.4 Drug release study

The release kinetics (and the local enlarged drawing) of SA from the hydrogels in water at 37 °C (that is simulated body temperature) are presented in Figure 5. In the overall view, the drug release behavior of all samples has finished in five hours. Specifically, the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite has the fastest release rate and it ends in 2h, while the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel has the slowest (about 5h), and the pure hydrogel has the release time about 3h. 66.0%, 73.72%, 46.13% are the final percentage of the drug release for the pure, the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel and the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel, individually. That is, the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel has the maximum drug release amount, the reason might be that the $-\text{COO}^-$ and the SA are both anionic so that the addition of the $-\text{COO}^-$ to the hydrogel promotes the release of the SA[26, 29]. The TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite has the minimum drug release amount. From the magnified part of the curves, it's obvious that the pure hydrogel has the fastest rate while the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel has the slowest rate during the first 45 minutes of drug release. Then after that the first 45 minutes, the rate of releasing drug of the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel exceeds the rate of the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel. It's shown that the three samples have distinct behaviors in drug release experiments.

Figure 5: Release patterns of SA from the hydrogel and composites at 37 °C

4 CONCLUSION

Novel thermo-sensitive hydrogel composites encapsulating with the covalent and non covalent functionalized CNTs have been designed and prepared by a free radical cross-linking polymerizing avenue. The SEM images show that the addition of the CNTs leads to thinner mesh walls and larger pores. The results of temperature responsive properties show that the TritonX-100-CNTs/hydrogel composite has a greater swelling rate and faster deswelling speed than the others. In the drug release study, the COOH-CNTs/hydrogel composite has a slower rate of SA release and a higher release

percentage. All these results show that different functionalized CNTs can be applied to achieve varied properties of hydrogel composites for controlled drug delivery system.

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